

STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT OF PRODUCTION ACTIVITY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Аннотация: Maqolada tashkilotga oid bir qancha izohlar berilgan sanoat korxonolari faoliyati va ularning tahlili moliyaviy ko'rsatkichlar. Natijalar ham taqdim etiladi ichida bozor munosabatlarining ahamiyati to'g'risida bir qator tadqiqotlar korxonalarining iqtisodiy faoliyatini tahlil qilish. Foydalanishning bir qator afzalliklariga misollar uchun ma'lumotlar bazasi sifatida moliyaviy hisobotlar moliyaviy ahvolini tahlil qilish, хулоса ва тавсиялар келтирилган.

Таянч сўзлар: iqtisod, moliyaviy tahli, mehnat bozor munosabatlari, foyda rentabellik, iqtisodiyotning sektorlari, sanoat korxonona, moliyaviy hisobotlar.

Аннотация: В статье дается ряд комментариев по организации деятельности промышленных предприятий и анализу их финансовых показателей. Также представлены результаты ряда исследований о значении рыночных отношений в анализе экономической деятельности предприятий. Приведены примеры ряда преимуществ использования финансовой отчетности в качестве базы данных для анализа финансового положения.

Ключевые слова: экономика, общество личности, анализ финансовых результатов, трудовые ресурсы, рыночные отношения, прибыль, рентабельность, секторы экономики, промышленные предприятия, финансовая отчетность.

Annotation: The article contains several comments on the organization, activity of industrial enterprises and their analysis of financial indicators. The results are also presented in a series of studies on the importance of market relations in the analysis of the economic activity of enterprises. Examples of a number of advantages of using financial statements as a database include analysis of the financial situation, conclusions and recommendations .

Key words: economy, financial analysis, labor market relations, profitability, sectors of the economy, industrial enterprise, financial statements.

Enter. Industrial enterprises must have a certain amount of means of production to carry out production activities.

Production items (materials, raw materials, fuel, etc.) are transformed into finished products at the end of the production process and constitute its core.

With the help of production funds (weapons, equipment, transport, transmission equipment, etc.), labor production transforms objects into finished products. Acocii funds participate in several stages of the production process and gradually wear out over time. The subject of production is completely used at one stage of the production process and turns into a product.

So, the means of production will completely transfer their value to the finished product. Production funds are transferred according to their gradual wear and tear and are involved in several stages of production.

Thus, fixed assets are a set of labor tools, expressed in the form of value (money), with a service life of not less than 1 year, which participate in the production process for a long time and transfer their cost to the finished product gradually, depending on their wear and tear.

Analysis and results

Each of the main funds or a group of them is accounted for in kind. For example, furnaces - usable area in m2, residential buildings - in number and usable area in m2.

In practice, the following methods of assessment of fixed assets are used:

1. At full cost:
 - a. main-primary baho;
 - b. in recovery.
2. According to the disposal cost of obsolete parts:
 - a. main-primary baho;
 - b. in recovery.
3. Appreciation in loss.

Amortization of fixed assets is a monetary expression of their physical and mental wear and tear. At the same time, depreciation determines the part of the cost of fixed assets transferred to the finished product. Physical wear and tear results from their use. There are 2 types of spiritual obsolescence:

- when it is developed more efficiently compared to the existing acoc iy funds;
- when it is produced cheaper than the existing basic funds.

Depreciation allowances, which are the monetary expression of physical and mental wear and tear, accumulate gradually and form the depreciation fund. The main funds are fully or partially restored from this fund account. Statistics distinguish between the annual depreciation amount and the depreciation rate when studying the depreciation of fixed assets. Annual depreciation amount _ year is the sum of the amortization amounts allocated during the period , which is determined based on the formula:

$$A_n = \frac{BBB + \text{ЙХ} - \text{ЙБ}}{T}$$

In this case: BBB is the full primary value of the object;

YX — costs of disposal of the used object (dismantling, separation, demolition, etc.);

YB - proceeds from the sale of materials, tools and other materials received during the construction of the object;

T is the service period of the object.

Indicators representing the movement and condition of the main funds

The name of K ' indicators	Calculation method
1. Action indicators	The value of new fixed assets
1.1. Reduction coefficient _ _	
1.2. Update factor i	End-of-year value of mutual funds
	The value of newly introduced fixed assets
	Value of fixed assets at the end of the year

1.3. Output factor	The value of fixed assets that have been exhausted
	The value of basic funds at the beginning of the year
	The value of lost reserve funds
2. Status indicators	The value of mutual funds at the beginning of the year
	Depreciation amount
2.1. Attrition rate	Full value of auxiliary funds
	Koldic clothing
2.2. Validity factor	Full coefficient of mutual funds

As can be seen from the data of Table 2, Jizzakh Plastics is a joint stock company society age up to 3 years has been main tools 4.2 percent in 2018 organize reached if so , by 2020 and 25.1 percent organize reached _ Meat everyone in society main of means this the highest share in the group was observed in 2019 and decreased to 18.2% in 2020. Because the existing fixed assets were released from this age group in 2020. Implementation of active investment policy during 2018-2020 as a result, the age group from 4 to 5 years and from 6 to 10 years tools share increased went _ from 10 years high young group share while has decreased over the years under study .

Table 2

Age structure of industrial production machines and equipment, which are part of the main assets of "Jizzakh plastic" joint stock company.

No	Young groups	Measurement unit	Years		
			2018 _	2019 _	20 20
1	3 years	percentage	4.2	43.3	25.1
		a thousand soum	230404.0	4201070.0	3988490.1
2	4 to 5 years	percentage	27.6	16.8	31.4
		a thousand soum	1515704.0	1630138.0	4983865.0
3	6 to 10 years	percentage	29.7	18.1	33.9
		a thousand soum	1634021.0	1756657.0	5388069.9
4	10 years high	percentage	38.5	21.8	9.5
		a thousand soum	2129891.0	2109672.0	1514019.4
Total main tools		percentage	100	100	100
		a thousand soum	5510020.0	9697537.0	1587444.4

In conclusion, it can be said that measures should be taken to fully demonstrate the investment potential of our country in order to attract foreign investments to increase the investment activity of accelerated depreciation in the regions. Also, the ability to apply accelerated depreciation in the economy leads to the formation of additional untaxed income of enterprises operating in the economy. Second, depreciation allowances are a stable source of profit, which, unlike other sources of profit, prevents production from falling into a crisis. Thirdly, depreciation allowances are private funds of the enterprise and lead to savings on various interest payments and serve to increase production efficiency. Fourthly, the availability of amortization funds leads to the acceleration of the process of development and modernization of enterprises in accordance with the market demand, as well as the expansion of production and improvement of product quality.

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